

Reversal Asymmetry of Reciprocal Metasurface Enables Ultra-Compact Varifocal Reflective Lens

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Reversing a ray through a conventional lens will bring it back to its starting point. Although such reversal symmetry is characteristic of reciprocal systems, such symmetry can be broken without violating reciprocity. This is demonstrated in the case when utilizing circular polarization states and chiral structures: Geometric phase metasurface lenses (metalenses) can be shown to act as positive (converging) or negative (diverging) lenses depending on transmission through the front or rear of the lens, respectively, for a given circular polarization state. Ray-tracing for such a metalens placed in front of a mirror reveals that reversal symmetry is broken: The reversed ray after the mirror does not end at the starting point. In this paper, such an arrangement is used to realize a varifocal reflective doublet that is equivalent to a transmissive doublet with a consecutive positive and negative lens. Such a reflective arrangement is not possible using a reversal symmetric lens, and allows for realizing an ultra-compact varifocal lens component. A proof-of-concept implementation using a 1550 nm NIR metalens is demonstrated, attaining a diopter change on the order of 1052 m^{-1} for a focal length shift of $240 \mu\text{m}$, caused by a $53 \mu\text{m}$ thin-film piezoelectric micromirror displacement.

1609 Galileo presented an improved telescope, which used convergent and divergent lenses that are easily recognizable as lenses today.^[3] Throughout this long history, lenses have been reversal symmetric: Reversing a ray through a conventional refractive lens will bring it back to its starting point. Equivalently, if a collimated beam is focused to a point, a point source placed at that focal point will result in a collimated beam in the reverse direction. In this sense one can state that a converging lens will act as a converging lens in both directions (even if its geometry is not reflection-symmetric, such as planoconvex lenses). The same applies to divergent lenses: A divergent lens in the forward direction, will act as a divergent lens in reverse.

Such lens symmetry is a tell-tale characteristic of reciprocity. Lorentz reciprocity usually implies that forward and backward transmission coefficients due to scatterers with symmetric permittivity

and permeability tensors, are equal. The opposite case, broken symmetry (or asymmetry), is however sometimes too quickly attributed to non-reciprocity. Care must be taken here: For instance it has recently been noted that geometric phase (GP) metasurfaces provide asymmetry in transmission for circular polarized (CP) light.^[4] These GP metasurfaces are of course fully reciprocal, being composed of linear and time-invariant media described by symmetric (or scalar) permittivity tensors. Below we show from direct application of the Lorentz reciprocity theorem that a scattering matrix arises that is not necessarily symmetric due to the non-real nature of CP light states.

It is worth pausing on this possibility of breaking reversal symmetry without violating reciprocity. When required to break symmetry in optical systems one usually needs complex and bulky non-reciprocal components (such as three-port circulator devices), because elementary optical components (e.g., lenses and filters) are typically reciprocal. Being able to break reversal symmetry with simple reciprocal components thereby allows for certain optical design freedom not frequently encountered. In this paper we make use of the asymmetry property of a GP metasurface lens (or metalens), referred to as a GPM from now onwards. I.e. we will use the property that the GPM is direction dependent for CP light, acting as a positive (converging) lens in

1. Introduction

The earliest known use of lenses dates back several thousands of years to ancient Egypt.^[1] A fairly modern concept of lenses arose already in 10th century AD when they were understood by the Persian mathematician Ibn Sahl in terms of refraction,^[2] and in

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Figure 1. Compact reflective varifocal metasurface lens (CRM) concept and its constituent components. a) Illustration of metasurface substrate placed on top of a MEMS-mirror. b) Image of MEMS-mirror. c) Image of metasurface lens. d) SEM image of metasurface structure (scalebar 2 μm). e, f) illustration of how the gap between the metasurface and mirror changes as the MEMS-mirror is actuated.

one direction, while acting as a negative (diverging) lens of equal strength in reverse for a given CP state. We utilize the freedom this provides to realize an ultra-compact reflective varifocal lens-doublet (as illustrated in **Figure 1** and discussed in Section 3). The transmission asymmetry allows the lens spacing to become vanishingly small, while maintaining large focal shifts. The planarity of the metalenses make these small gap regions accessible, and contributes to the small overall form factor. MEMS actuation of the GPM-mirror gap is a natural candidate for realizing a compact system, particularly given the fact that metasurfaces can be integrated into MEMS fabrication.^[5–7] The planar architectures of both metalens and MEMS allow for simplicity in wafer-level fabrication, as will be further discussed in Section 3.2.

MEMS-actuated lenses offer fast, small, lightweight, and cost-effective tunability of relevance to miniaturized optical tunable lenses.^[8] These are properties necessary for a wide range of applications from biological imaging to applications on drones or robots.^[9,10] There exist micro-optical techniques by which a single lens can be tuned (e.g., by deformation of polymer lenses^[11,12] or modulating the refractive index in e.g., liquid crystal lenses^[13,14]). However, for faster actuation rates and stronger modulations, MEMS-displaced lens doublets have emerged as a promising platform:^[6] These include both modulating the gaps between metalenses^[15,16] and sideways translation of Alvarez metalenses.^[17,18] For MEMS based optical devices, the tunability is often constrained by the available MEMS displacement range. On that note, thin-film piezoelectric MEMS (piezoMEMS) has been proposed due to its ability to offer long-stroke quasi-static displacement at low voltages. Thin-film piezoMEMS was first ap-

plied to plasmonic metasurfaces in our earlier work.^[19] We later applied a piezoMEMS actuation to a varifocal transmissive silicon metalens doublet with a maximum displacement of 7.2 μm .^[16] Here, we utilize a novel thin-film piezoelectric PZT MEMS actuator to offer an order of magnitude larger mirror modulation distance of 62 μm at 40 V. We demonstrate a NIR tunable lens with large diopter change on the order of 1052 m^{-1} . The resulting compact reflective metalens (CRM) can be operated up to kHz range and is inherently low power (on the order of 500 nW) due to utilizing thin-film piezoelectric PZT actuators.

2. Theory

2.1. Reversal Asymmetry in Reciprocal Lens Gives Direction-Dependent Focusing

The well known Lorentz-reciprocity theorem^[20–22] has several implications for light scattering systems, such as metasurfaces. As mentioned, Lorentz reciprocity usually implies that forward and backward transmission coefficients due to scatterers with symmetric permittivity and permeability tensors, are equal. As an example, consider **Figure 2a** where the source (port 1) is placed at the focal point of a conventional refractive lens and port 2 is taken to be the intersection of a resulting collimated ray and a mirror. Light reflected at port 2 is reflected back to port 1 (according to the basic function of a lens). This is an example of equivalence in interchanging source and detector, which is so common in reciprocal systems that it sometimes is mistakenly assumed to be the case for all reciprocal systems. However, as we shall now see,

Figure 2. a) Conventional lens placed in front of a mirror for which reversal symmetry is observed: A ray from the focal point 1 is reflected at point 2 and returns to point 1. b) A geometric phase metasurface lens (GPM) is placed in front of a mirror for which the reversal symmetry is broken when using circular polarized states: Light reflected at point 2 is redirected to point 3 rather than returning to point 1.

Lorentz-reciprocity does not always dictate such reversal symmetry.

Consider Figure 2b in which a similar setup is made with CP states and a chiral GP metalens. We consider a ray of left circular polarized light $|L\rangle$ propagating from the focal point of the GP metalens (GPM), i.e., port 1. The GPM applies the phase retardation of a focusing lens to the cross-polarized CP state, according to the principle of geometric phase.^[7,23,24] After the GPM, the resulting cross-polarized (right circular) ray $|R\rangle$ is therefore collimated and intersects the mirror at port 2. Mirror reflection from port 2 again cross-polarizes to $|L\rangle$. Upon returning through the GPM once again, this time entering through the rear, the chirality of the GPM is reversed (as discussed in further detail below) and the ray is therefore sent to a port 3, instead of back to port 1. From the illustration in Figure 2b, one observes that the GPM therefore acts as a convergent lens for $|L\rangle$ rays propagating from 1, while acting as a divergent lens for $|L\rangle$ rays reflected from 2. In the next section, we discuss how this property of direction dependent focusing is utilized to realize an ultra-compact reflective varifocal lens.

The GPM is a linear, time-symmetric and spatially non-dispersive system, and as such obeys Lorentz reciprocity. Despite this, clear reflection asymmetry is observed in Figure 2b: Light reflected at terminal 2 is sent to terminal 3 rather than terminal 1, in contrast to the symmetric case of the conventional lens in Figure 2a. We shall now show that such asymmetry is permitted by the Lorentz-Reciprocity theorem and explain how it occurs from Jones matrix formalism. Since CP modes cannot be written real, there are complications related to orthogonality. Let \mathbf{e}_j and \mathbf{h}_j be the electric and magnetic (transversal) modal fields of mode j . Define

$$B_{jk} = \int \mathbf{e}_j \times \mathbf{h}_k^* \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{jk} = \int \mathbf{e}_j \times \mathbf{h}_k \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (2)$$

where we integrate over the transversal plane. Equation (1) is the usual inner product between electromagnetic modes, while Equation (2) is a corresponding expression without complex conjugate. For real, linearly polarized modes there is no difference between Equations (1) and (2), but for complex modes there is. In the Lorentz reciprocity theorem, there is no complex conjugate for the magnetic field, and consequently, it is the version in Equation (2) that is needed to determine the properties of the scattering matrix. A full treatment of Lorentz reciprocity (see ref. [22]) reveals that it is the matrix CS , where S is the scattering matrix, that is symmetric.

Consider circular polarization modes

$$\mathbf{e}_{\pm} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \pm i \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{h}_{\pm} = \begin{bmatrix} \pm 1 \\ i \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the magnetic field has been found from the electric field using Faraday's law (omitting unimportant constants). By direct calculation we find

$$B_{++} = B_{--} = C_{+-} = C_{-+} \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

$$B_{+-} = B_{-+} = C_{++} = C_{--} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Thus we have orthogonal modes in the sense of the inner product in Equation (1) but not in the sense of Equation (2). Moreover, C is not proportional to the identity, but acts as a permutation matrix. It therefore follows that the scattering matrix S is not necessarily symmetric, although CS is. For further discussion on this matter, see Section 5.

We now proceed to calculate specific transmission coefficients by use of Jones matrix formalism. Phase retardations by the GP metasurface are applied to the cross-polarized CP state through pointwise rotations $\alpha(r)$ of geometrically identical subunit metasurface structures (as illustrated in Figure 3). Assuming transmission coefficients t_x and t_y for x- and y-polarized light incident on the GP metasurface, an expression for the transmitted light can be found through Jones matrix formalism and straightforward application of rotation matrices and a basis change to circular polarization states (see Section S4, Supporting Information):

$$\text{GPM}(\alpha)|L\rangle = \frac{t_x + t_y}{2}|L\rangle + \frac{t_x - t_y}{2}e^{i2\alpha}|R\rangle \quad (6)$$

$$\text{GPM}(\alpha)|R\rangle = \frac{t_x + t_y}{2}|R\rangle + \frac{t_x - t_y}{2}e^{-i2\alpha}|L\rangle \quad (7)$$

here $\text{GPM}(\alpha)$ denotes the local operation of the GPM when the metasurface subunit has rotation angle α . By suitable design of asymmetric metasurface subunits, a π phase difference can be imparted between the transmission coefficients, i.e., $t_y = -t_x$, yielding full cross-polarization after transmission through the GPM.

To easily understand the asymmetric transmission through the GPM, consider Figure 3. This illustrates a GP metasurface lens consisting of rectangular subunits where the rotation angles $\alpha(r)$ are found by pointwise sampling the phase function $\theta(r)$ of a

Figure 3. The front (a) and (b) rear side view of a metasurface, corresponding to a reflection transform (or equivalently a rotation) about the depicted y -axis, are observed from the inserts to be equal to a sign change in the rotations α .

positive lens, according to $\alpha(r) = \theta(r)/2$. Figure 3b illustrates the reflection transform of the GP metasurface upon reflecting the array about the indicated y -axis. Equivalently, this is the same GP metasurface as seen from its rear. From the inserts in the figures it is observed that the reflection transform in this case is equal to a sign change in the rotations of the rectangular subunits. Since the rotations impart the geometric phase, it follows that the rear side of the metasurface imparts a phase function of opposite sign, i.e., $-\theta(r)$, to that of the front side. Thus, if the front side implements a positive (convergent) lens of focal length $|f|$, then the rear side implements a negative (divergent) lens of equal focal length magnitude $|f|$. This is the origin of the direction dependent focusing of the GPM.

Note that flipping a GP metasurface will not always be equivalent to a sign change in its subunit rotations. This applies specifically when the reflection transform of the metasurface yields a structure that in each unit cell is identical apart from a sign change in rotation. A sufficient condition for this is when i) a global symmetry ensures that a subunit structure of identical geometry is flipped to the same position (in our case this is ensured by the circular symmetry of the lens phase function $\theta(r)$), and (ii) identical subunits are used that are themselves reflection symmetric (in our case this is ensured by the rectangular shaped subunits).

3. Compact Varifocal Reflective Metalens (CRM)

3.1. Design of CRM

The reflection asymmetry of GP metasurfaces for CP light allows for novel design freedom not typically available in systems relying on reciprocal elements. In this paper, we use the direction dependent focusing property of the GPM to realize the reflective lens doublet shown in Figure 4a: The GPM placed in front of a mirror accepts the incoming collimated light $|L\rangle$ and focuses the cross-polarized light $|R\rangle$ to an effective focal point a distance f_{eff} from

the GPM. The gray shaded area of the figure represents a reflection of the system, and shows the equivalent transmissive system leading to the same tunability. Note that for conventional reciprocal lenses, a reflective doublet will only be equivalent to transmissive doublets consisting of identical lenses (positive-positive or negative-negative). In contrast, the reversal asymmetry of the GPM allows us to depict a reflective doublet corresponding to a positive-negative doublet.

The GPM-mirror gap L influences the effective focal distance f_{eff} . Whereas the center operation gap for a positive-positive lens doublet is equal to twice the focal lengths of the lenses $L = 2f$, i.e., the gap at which the doublet switches between being converging or diverging, the operation gap for our depicted GPM system is $L \rightarrow 0$ since it represents a positive-negative lens doublet. The depicted compact reflective metalens (CRM) is therefore ultra-compact owing both to the planar metalens and the vanishing operation gaps $L \rightarrow 0$. Notice also that the GPM-mirror distance L is half of the corresponding gap in the transmissive system. This is advantageous when the available gap modulation distance is limited. As will be discussed in Section 3.2, these mentioned properties furthermore make the design particularly suited for mass-production using silicon process and MEMS technology.

Using a thin lens model, a simple relationship between the effective focal length f_{eff} , the GPM-mirror gap L and the GPM focal length $|f|$ can be derived

$$f_{\text{eff}} = -\frac{|f|(2L + |f|)}{2L} \quad (8)$$

Note that the mirror separation is here assumed to be negative $L = -|L|$ having placed the coordinate origin at the GPM. The normalized effective focal length shift vs GPM-mirror gap is shown in Figure 4b. As expected one observes rapid change in the focal length f_{eff} close to zero gap $L = 0$. The effective focal point asymptotically approaches $f_{\text{eff}} \rightarrow -|f|$ at large gaps. This is as expected, as the asymptote corresponds with the image point

Figure 4. a) A reflective lens doublet using a geometric phase metalens (GPM) combined with a mirror. The mirrored system is also drawn (within the gray region) showing that this reflective arrangement is equivalent to a transmissive arrangement of a positive and negative lens with twice the spacing $2L$. b) A normalized plot of effective focal lengths of the CRM vs normalized metalens-mirror displacement utilizing the thin-lens model and a ray tracing (zemax) simulation.

for the last (negative) lens when the object is placed at infinity. At $L = -|f|/4$ the effective focal length in Equation (8) becomes equal to the focal length of the metalens $f_{\text{eff}} = |f|$. Therefore, a modulation displacement range corresponding to 25% of the focal length of the GPM is a meaningful target value when choosing the relevant mirror actuation principle (Section 3.2) to ensure large diopter changes in the resulting tunable reflective lens. Due to the flat-lens nature of the GPM, the approximation of a thin lens turns out to be accurate for our experiments, as verified by ray-tracing simulations using Zemax (Section S2, Supporting Information).

The preceding discussion assumes a GPM designed to act as a positive lens upon first transmission for incident left circular light $|L\rangle$. If instead oppositely polarized light (i.e., $|R\rangle$) is applied to such a device, Equations (6) and (7) shows that it becomes equivalent with a doublet consisting of consecutive negative and positive lenses with equal focal length magnitudes. For this doublet the asymptote instead becomes $f_{\text{eff}} \rightarrow +|f|$ as $L \rightarrow -\infty$. Thus, switching the CP state allows for switching between curves of focal point positions, and using linearly polarized light (a superposition of equal amounts of $|L\rangle$ and $|R\rangle$) allows for the realization of a bifocal tunable lens.

3.2. MEMS-Micromirror for Long Stroke Mirror Displacements

An advantage of metasurface lenses is that they can be fabricated using standard silicon process technology. As such it is natural to consider the use of Micro-Electro-Mechanical-Systems (MEMS) as actuators for the CRM, which can be fabricated in similar process lines. Since the GPM-mirror gaps can be vanishingly small $L \rightarrow 0$, this allows for a simple assembly process whereby the wafer containing metalenses and the wafer containing MEMS mirrors can simply be bonded together on wafer-level, without the need for added spacer elements in between. Suitable equipment in a cleanroom environment are prerequisites to ensure high yield of such bonded MEMS-mirror

die over a wafer. An advantage in us using piezoelectric actuators is that they do not face the same issues with stiction upon close proximity actuations as those faced by electrostatic actuators.

We have previously demonstrated a piezoelectric actuated micromirror which can achieve tilting motion of ± 0.5 degrees and translational “piston” motion of $7.2 \mu\text{m}$.^[16,25] A suspended central circular gold mirror of diameter 3mm is actuated by applying voltages to a thin-film PZT piezoelectric membrane encircling it, deposited on typically $700 \mu\text{m}$ wide and $10 \mu\text{m}$ thin actuator arms. A similar concept is realized here, using a cascade of concentric actuator-rings to increase the stroke-length. Here, the downward/upward push/pull of diameter 3 mm, $400 \mu\text{m}$ thick, planar gold-plated central mirror is generated by actuating four independent rings of thin film PZT actuator-pairs. As shown in Figure 5, biasing the inner actuators relative to the mirror, pushes the mirror down, while biasing the outer rings pulls it up. It is found that $10 \mu\text{m}$ thick membrane sections of around $700 \mu\text{m}$ width maximize the piston stroke-length while maintaining mirror-planarity and stability, given the mechanical boundary-conditions for the present design.

A vertical displacement of up to $\pm 31 \mu\text{m}$ (a $62 \mu\text{m}$ total stroke) at 40 V of applied voltage has been measured using white light interferometry, as shown in Figure 5. This is an order of magnitude larger than that of our previously reported micromirror.^[16,25] To characterize the resonance frequencies of our MEMS devices we have utilized impedance spectroscopy on a similar architecture (a device with additional sectioning of the electrodes to allow for tip/tilt motions), which indicates resonances at 3.37 and 3.26 kHz at piston-up and piston-down motions, respectively.

Thin-film piezoelectric MEMS has the advantage of requiring ultra low power. Measuring the power consumption at static actuation gives values on the order for 500 nW at 23 V. Please refer to Section S5 (Supporting Information) for details on resonance frequency and power consumption measurements. Fur-

Figure 5. Long-stroke piezo-electric MEMS-micromirror. a) Cross-sectional height profile of the micromirror as measured by white-light interferometry. The mirror height corresponding to three distinct actuation states is shown. At a 40 V application to the innermost electrodes, the PZT membrane pulls the ring downward, placing the mirror at its lowest position. Conversely, a 40 V application to the outermost electrodes causes the PZT membrane to draw the ring upward, resulting in the highest position. In the absence of voltage, an intermediate position is achieved. Notably, a displacement range of 62 μm is observed, and a high level of planarity is maintained throughout movement. b) Presents 3D images of the MEMS mirror at the three specified actuation states. c) Illustration of wafer-level batch processing of CRM lenses.

thermore, thin-film piezoelectric PZT MEMS can offer long-term durability and reliability making them relevant for wide range of applications.^[26,27]

3.3. Metasurface Fabrication

The metasurface design employed in this publications targeted an operation wavelength of 1550 nm and was fabricated in silicon by use of UV-nanoimprint lithography (UV-NIL) patterning of resist and subsequent Bosch Deep Reactive Ion Etching (DRIE). The resulting structures are shown in Figure 6a,b, and an illustration of the process flow is given in Figure 6c.

A metalens of size $300 \times 300 \mu\text{m}$ was utilized, containing rectangular pillars with target dimensions of widths $w = 237 \text{ nm}$, lengths $l = 361 \text{ nm}$, heights $h = 1200 \text{ nm}$, and pitches of the square unit cells of $p = 835 \text{ nm}$. The metasurface encodes a phase function that was determined through Zemax optimization of a transmissive doublet (in the CRM configuration) over a range of interlens spacings $2L \in [25 \mu\text{m}, 45 \mu\text{m}]$, where additionally the condition that the two lenses should have the same phase function apart from a sign change was applied. As shown in the Section S2 (Supporting Information), the resulting phase function is a compromise between different focal lengths, but for small radii approaches that of $|f| \approx 230 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 6a,b shows the metasurface structures achieved. We have previously published a detailed account of this process offering structures with good pattern fidelity that result GP metalenses with diffraction limited focusing and efficiencies on the order of 40–50% over the wavelength range 1.30–1.55 μm (the

primary loss mechanism being reflections at the Si-air interface of the metasurface).^[7]

4. Experimental Validation of Lens Concept

To verify the compact reflective metalens concept (CRM) we use the long-stroke piezoelectric MEMS mirror described in Section 3.2 in the setup shown in Figure 7a. We utilize a metalens of focal length $|f| \approx 230 \mu\text{m}$ (Section 3.3) that corresponds well with the available MEMS displacement range, to ensure large diopter changes (as discussed in Section 3.1). Figures 7b,c show focusing and defocusing of the CRM by changing the micromirror-metalens separation. Note that when the metalens and mirror are well-aligned and parallel a strong back reflection (from the air-silicon interface) occurs, which obstructs the visibility of the focused spot. With an assumed metalens efficiency on the order of 50% (Section 3.3), and accounting for air-silicon reflections, the focusing efficiency is expected to be below 12%. The back reflections can be significantly reduced by switching to glass substrates for which metalens efficiencies of above 90% can be achieved^[28] and applying AR-coatings to the substrate backside. The spot quality can be further improved by better methods of aligning the 300 μm sized metalens with its mirror reflection and ensuring planarity. The observed focus spot quality is nevertheless sufficient to verify the CRM concept.

The MEMS micromirror is mounted on a ThorLabs 6-axis kinematic mount, allowing precise control over X, Y, Z, tip, tilt, and roll movements for fine orientation and alignment relative to the metalens. This assembly is attached to an XYZ translational stage, offering 10-microns precision and a 25 mm movement

(a) Cross-section

(b) Top view

(c) Fabrication process flow using UV-nanoimprint lithography.

Figure 6. a–b): SEM images of fabricated Silicon metasurface by UV-Nanoimprint lithography and Bosch DRIE etching. c) Metasurface fabrication process flow. 1. Stamp fabrication: Spin-on stamp material on silicon master template containing EBL fabricated metasurface, and curing of stamp. 2. Imprint: Application of stamp to resist-coated silicon wafer. Curing by UV. 3. Etch: First residual polymer layer must be removed by a direct etch, before subsequent Bosch Deep Reactive Ion Etching. 4. Finalization: After resist removal by plasma, metalens is completed. Details on process are given in our previous work.^[7]

range for coarse positioning. The metalens is similarly mounted on an XYZ translational stage for relative movement control. Outer electrodes of the MEMS mirror are actuated at 30 V, pushing the central mirror toward the metalens (Section 3.2). The XYZ stage then brings the MEMS mirror close to the metalens, with the contact point easily identified by distortion in the focal spot on the camera. Ideally, the micromirror is initially positioned just short of contact with the metalens, but in practice non-planarity

between mirror and metalens results in a small gap to arise. The objective lens, mounted on a 2D mechanical stage and a motorized linear translation stage (of 1 μm step accuracy), is adjusted to find the precise focal point at this closest mirror-metalens separation. Voltage to the outer electrodes of the micromirror is then reduced in steps of 10 V, increasing the micromirror-metalens separation each time. This moves the focal spot, which is re-focused by moving the objective lens closer to the micromirror-metalens

(a) Focus

(b) Focus

(c) Defocus

Figure 7. Tuning the effective focal length using piezo-electric MEMS mirror and metalens with $|f| \approx 230 \mu\text{m}$. a) Schematic of setup used. b,c) Images of focus (b) and defocus (c) upon varying the metalens-mirror distance.

Figure 8. Tuning the effective focal length using piezoelectric MEMS micromirror and a $|f| \approx 230 \mu\text{m}$ metalens. a) Left axis: Experimentally measured focal length shift versus voltage actuation. Right axis: Experimentally measured mirror displacement versus voltage application. b) Here we assign the experimentally measured changes in focal length Δf_{meas} versus changes in mirror-lens separation ΔL to the absolute positions that minimize RMSE relative to the thin-lens model for $|f| = 230 \mu\text{m}$.

using the motorized translation stage (the effective focal length decreases with increasing micromirror-metalens separation). At zero voltage application to the outer electrodes of the micromirror, voltage is then applied to the inner electrodes to continue the mirror movement away from the metalens. Measurements of the focal point positions are thus conducted for seven voltage applications. The measured focal distance f_{meas} is calculated by first finding the focal point with the objective lens, and then subtracting the working distance of the objective lens (20mm) from the estimated distance between the metalens and the objective lens. Note that f_{meas} differs from the expression f_{eff} derived in Equation (8) by a correction factor that accounts for the silicon substrate on which the metalens is fabricated. Under paraxial assumptions the correction factor is expressed $t(1 - n_{\text{air}}/n_{\text{si}})$, where $t = 500 \mu\text{m}$ and $n_{\text{si}} = 3.46$ are the thickness and refractive index of the silicon substrate at $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, and $n_{\text{air}} = 1$ is the refractive index of air (see Section S3, Supporting Information).

Figure 8a presents the change in focal length versus applied voltage to the MEMS-actuated CRM. Micromirror displacements corresponding to voltage application are also shown from separate white-light interferometric measurements (Figure 5), and are added to the right y-axis of Figure 8a. The experimental results demonstrate a focal shift of $\Delta f_{\text{meas}} = \Delta f_{\text{eff}} = 240 \mu\text{m}$ for a micromirror displacement of $\Delta L = 53 \mu\text{m}$ from an actuation voltage of 30 V between outer and inner electrodes.

Figure 8b compares the measured changes in focal points and mirror-lens separations to the thin lens model derived in Section 3.1 (with added Si substrate correction factor). The uncertainty in absolute positions of the focal points and spacings exceeds scales of the plot: As observed from Figure 7a, measuring the absolute position of the focal length requires challenging measurement of the distance in free space from metalens to focal point through a beamsplitter. Measuring the mirror-lens spacing to micrometer-precision in free space is also challenging given the minute spacing and the issues non-planarity give for

assessing the initial spacing. However, the positions of the measurement points relative to one another is known with greater accuracy: Moving the objective lens is performed using a motorized translation stage of $1 \mu\text{m}$ step accuracy and relative adjustments of micromirror-metalens spacing L are performed by the piezoelectric MEMS actuation characterized in Figures 5 and 8a. Therefore, treating the absolute measured values for f_{meas} and L as unknown, but the relative values Δf_{meas} and ΔL as known, we fit the data to the thin lens-model Equation (8) in such a way that minimizes the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). As discussed in Section 3.3 and Section S2 (Supporting Information), note that the phase function of the fabricated metalens is not a pure lens function, but can be interpreted as a compromise between different focal lengths around $|f| \approx 230 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting fit shows the data qualitatively following the trend curve for $|f| = 230 \mu\text{m}$. In the Section S2 (Supporting Information) the experiment is repeated for a metalens of focal length $|f| = 10 \text{mm}$ and a manually displaced mirror where the longer length scales make the precision of absolute positioning sufficient to avoid the need for such fitting. Here also agreement is observed between measurements and the model.

According to the thin lens model in Figure 8b, a large diopter change of up to 1600m^{-1} can be attained when moving the mirror from $L_1 = 0$ to $L_2 = -53 \mu\text{m}$. As mentioned it is challenging to start at $L_1 = 0$ without perfect planarity between micromirror and metasurface, in addition to a $10 \mu\text{m}$ step down from the actuator ring to the mirror element (visible in the cross-sectional image in Figure 5). Utilizing the mirror displacement range $\Delta L = 53 \mu\text{m}$ at larger initial gaps $L_1 < 0$ correspondingly leads to smaller diopter modulations. As such it is as expected that the measured focal point positions corresponding to Figure 8b indicate a lower diopter shift, on the order of 1052m^{-1} . This is however still a considerable diopter change.

Given the substrate thickness $t = 500 \mu\text{m}$, the estimated focal points have been shifted from air into the silicon substrate during the MEMS modulation. Within the silicon, both the CRM fo-

Figure 9. Sending circular polarized (CP) light through a) front and b) rear of a geometric phase metasurface. Notice that flipping the GPM involves a sign change of the rotation angles α .

cal point and the working distance of the objective lens become shifted relative to their position in air due to refraction. It is however straightforward to show that the shifts in the focal point and working distance compensate each other, so that the measured focal distance under the setup described above is equivalent to measuring the focal distance outside of the silicon (see Section S3, Supporting Information where both analytical paraxial calculations and numerical ray tracing simulations demonstrate this).

5. Discussion: Lorentz Reciprocity and the Scattering Matrix of the GPM

Figure 2b shows asymmetric behavior, since the reflected ray at point 2 does not end up at point 1. Still, we know that the system must obey Lorentz reciprocity, being composed of linear and time-invariant media described by symmetric (or scalar) permittivity tensors. Here we will add some further comments on how the behavior in Figure 2b is consistent with the Lorentz reciprocity theorem. It was shown in Section 2 that when modes are non-orthogonal and/or cannot be written real, the scattering matrix is not necessarily symmetric even when the system respects Lorentz reciprocity.^[22] This is the case when describing the system with circular polarized input and output modes.

A safe solution is therefore to apply the reciprocity relation to linearly polarized modes, and subsequently translate to circular polarization by change of basis. This was done in Section 2. For the case $t_y = -t_x$ the forward operation in Equations (6) and (7) reduce to

$$\text{GPM}(\alpha)|L\rangle = t_x e^{i2\alpha} |R\rangle \quad (9)$$

$$\text{GPM}(\alpha)|R\rangle = t_x e^{-i2\alpha} |L\rangle \quad (10)$$

Since Lorentz reciprocity means that the transmission coefficients for linear polarization (t_x and t_y) are the same for both directions, the backward operation is described by

$$\text{GPM}(-\alpha)|L\rangle = t_x e^{-i2\alpha} |R\rangle \quad (11)$$

$$\text{GPM}(-\alpha)|R\rangle = t_x e^{i2\alpha} |L\rangle \quad (12)$$

Figure 9 illustrates the results Equations (9) and (12). In Figure 9a the state $|L\rangle$ gets transmitted to $e^{i2\alpha}|R\rangle$, while in Figure 9b $|R\rangle$ gets reverse transmitted to $e^{i2\alpha}|L\rangle$. This may perhaps seem quite natural in light of reciprocity. However it is important to note that the forward polarization state $|R\rangle$ after a mirror reflection is denoted $|L\rangle$. This means that Figure 9 does not imply that the transmitted state, after a reflection, experiences the same transmission coefficient on the way back. Rather, Equations (9) and (11) show that the reverse transmission coefficient has opposite sign for the phase.

We now return to the derivation in Equations (1-5) in Section 2 to continue calculation of the scattering matrix S of the GP metasurface using C which acts as a permutation matrix in the case of CP modes. Considering two polarization modes on each side of the device, using Equations (4) and (5) and the fact that CS is symmetric (by the Lorentz reciprocity theorem^[22]), one finds after some algebra e.g., that

$$S_{\text{front+}, \text{rear-}} = S_{\text{rear+}, \text{front-}} \quad (13)$$

$$S_{\text{front+}, \text{rear-}} \neq S_{\text{rear-}, \text{front+}} \quad (14)$$

Here, for example, “front+” denotes a polarization mode e_+ at the front side of the device.

In the derivation of Equation (13) and (14), we have used a fixed coordinate system which does not depend on the direction of propagation. This means that the mode with electric field e_+ is right-handed $|R\rangle$ or left-handed $|L\rangle$ dependent on the direction of propagation. But e_+ is the physical electric field that is unchanged during reflection. (Or, strictly speaking, it picks up an irrelevant sign shift.) The result Equations (13) and (14) is therefore consistent with the results Equations (9-12).

6. Conclusion

This work presents the possibility of breaking the reversal symmetry of a lens and utilizes this to make an ultra-compact reflective varifocal metalens. This is done by use of a geometric phase metalens which can both act as a positive (converging) or negative (diverging) lens for a given circular polarization state, depending on transmission through the front or rear of the lens, respectively. Combining it with a mirror that can be displaced relative to the metasurface results in a varifocal reflective doublet that is equivalent to a transmissive doublet with a consecutive positive and negative lens. This feature is not possible with a reversal symmetric lens. The doublet achieves large focal length shifts at vanishing metalens-mirror gap modulations, making it well suited for MEMS-actuation and high-volume wafer-level silicon processing.

A proof-of-concept implementation using a 1550 nm NIR metalens is demonstrated, coupled with a novel long stroke (62 μm at 40 V) and high resonance frequency (kHz) piezoelectric MEMS-micromirror. The metasurface displacement range achieved by this MEMS-mirror surpasses that of state-of-the-art actuation by more than an order of magnitude, and theoretically enables a considerable diopter change on the order of 1600 m^{-1} . Our proof-of-concept implementation demonstrated a diopter change of around 1052 m^{-1} . The experimental outcomes agree with simulations and derived models. The large focal length shifts and diopter changes enabled is of relevance to a wide range of micro-optical applications within sensing and imaging.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that a patent has been filed relating to the concepts presented in this paper titled "Light Manipulating Apparatus" with UK Patent Application Number 2320140.3.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

Keywords

MOEMS, metasurface, piezoelectric MEMS, tunable lens

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- [1] J. M. Enoch, *J. Mod. Opt.* **2007**, *54*, 1221.
- [2] R. Rashed, *Isis* **1990**, *81*, 464.
- [3] S. Dupr, Ph.D. thesis, Ghent University, **2002**.
- [4] V. Fedotov, P. Mlyadonov, S. Prosvirnin, A. Rogacheva, Y. Chen, N. Zheludev, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2006**, *97*, 167401.
- [5] R.-J. Xu, Y.-S. Lin, *Electronics* **2022**, *11*, 243.
- [6] S. He, H. Yang, Y. Jiang, W. Deng, W. Zhu, *Micromachines* **2019**, *10*, 8.
- [7] C. A. Dirdal, K. Milenko, A. Summanwar, F. T. Dullo, P. C. Thrane, O. Rasoga, A. M. Avram, A. Dinescu, A. M. Baracu, *Nanomaterials* **2023**, *13*, 436.
- [8] C. Liu, T. Wang, X. Wang, M. Chang, Y. Jian, W. Wang, *Micromachines* **2025**, *16*, 482.
- [9] J. Kim, J. Seong, Y. Yang, S.-W. Moon, T. Badloe, J. Rho, *Adv. Photonics* **2022**, *4*, 024001.
- [10] M. Jablonowski, *Senses Soc.* **2020**, *15*, 344.
- [11] S. M. Kamali, E. Arbabi, A. Arbabi, Y. Horie, A. Faraon, *Laser Photonics Rev.* **2016**, *10*, 1002.
- [12] A. She, S. Zhang, S. Shian, D. R. Clarke, F. Capasso, *Sci. Adv.* **2018**, *4*, eaap9957.
- [13] M. Bosch, M. R. Shcherbakov, K. Won, H.-S. Lee, Y. Kim, G. Shvets, *Nano Lett.* **2021**, *21*, 3849.
- [14] J. Zhong, N. An, N. Yi, M. Zhu, Q. Song, S. Xiao, *Plasmonics* **2016**, *11*, 537.
- [15] E. Arbabi, A. Arbabi, S. M. Kamali, Y. Horie, M. Faraji-Dana, A. Faraon, *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, *9*, 1.
- [16] C. A. Dirdal, P. C. V. Thrane, F. T. Dullo, J. Gjessing, A. Summanwar, J. Tschudi, *Opt. Lett.* **2022**, *47*, 1049.
- [17] Z. Han, S. Colburn, A. Majumdar, K. F. Böhringer, *Microsyst. Nanoeng.* **2020**, *6*, 79.
- [18] Z. Han, S. Colburn, A. Majumdar, K. F. Böhringer, *Sci. Rep.* **2022**, *12*, 5385.
- [19] C. Meng, P. C. Thrane, F. Ding, J. Gjessing, M. Thomaschewski, C. Wu, C. Dirdal, S. I. Bozhevolnyi, *Sci. Adv.* **2021**, *7*, eabg5639.
- [20] L. D. Landau, E. M. Lifshitz, *Electrodynamics of continuous media*, Pergamon Press, New York and London, **1960**.
- [21] D. M. Pozar, *Microwave engineering*, 2nd edn, Wiley, New York **1998**.
- [22] G. K. Svendsen, M. W. Haakestad, J. Skaar, *Phys. Rev. A* **2013**, *87*, 013838.
- [23] M. Khorasaninejad, W. T. Chen, R. C. Devlin, J. Oh, A. Y. Zhu, F. Capasso, *Science* **2016**, *352*, 1190.
- [24] C. A. Dirdal, G. U. Jensen, H. Angelskár, P. C. V. Thrane, J. Gjessing, D. A. Ordnung, *Opt. Express* **2020**, *28*, 15542.
- [25] T. Bakke, A. Vogl, O. Žero, F. Tyholdt, I.-R. Johansen, D. Wang, *J. Microelectromech. Microeng.* **2010**, *20*, 064010.
- [26] R. P. Dahl-Hansen, F. Tyholdt, J. Gjessing, A. Vogl, P. Wittendorp, J. Vedum, T. Tybell, *J. Microelectromech. Syst.* **2020**, *30*, 105.
- [27] R. Dahl-Hansen, J. Gjessing, P. Mardilovich, C. Fragkiadakis, J. Thorstensen, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2022**, *121*, 13.
- [28] V. Egede Johansen, U. M. Gür, J. Martínez-Llinás, J. Fly Hansen, A. Samadi, M. Skak Vestergaard Larsen, T. Nielsen, F. Mattinson, M. Schmidlin, N. A. Mortensen, U. J. Quaade, *Commun. Phys.* **2024**, *7*, 123.